

Table S2. Characteristics of alignments, partition-merging results and best substitution model for each partition according to Bayesian information criterion

Alignment	Length (bp)	Variable position	Partitioning scheme (substitution model)
ITS, <i>tefl-α</i> & <i>tubb</i>	1644	74	Seven partitions: ITS1 & ITS2 (TrN+G); 5.8S (K80); 1 st codon positions of <i>tefl-α</i> (F81+I); 1 st codon positions of <i>tubb</i> ; 2 nd codon positions of <i>tubb</i> & <i>tefl-α</i> (JC); 3 rd codon positions of <i>tubb</i> & <i>tefl-α</i> (HKY+I); introns of <i>tubb</i> & <i>tefl-α</i> (K80+I+G)
ITS	594	22	Two partitions: ITS1 & ITS2 (TrN+G); 5.8S (K80)
<i>tefl-α</i>	605	36	Three partitions: 1 st & 2 nd codon positions (JC); 3 rd codon positions (HKY+I); introns (K80)
<i>tubb</i>	445	16	Three partitions: 1 st & 2 nd codon positions (JC); 3 rd codon positions (HKY); introns (K80+G)